

Educational Status of Bundi District: A Geographical Study

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Abstract

Literacy is an important demographic element of the human development process. All the developing countries are addressing the challenges of education for all since education is a most powerful instrument for the alleviation of poverty and inequality in society. Literacy contributes to better health, higher productivity, high income, capability and esteemed living, increased participation in community life. The modern concept of education means to develop the inherent capacities of a child. The aim of the present paper is to find out the educational status of Bundi district.

The educational status has been worked out at primary, secondary and at higher secondary educational levels. The paper also aims to find out the decadal changes and highlight the causes of regional variations.

Keywords: Literacy, Spatial Pattern, Male Literacy, Female Literacy, Regional Variation.

Introduction

Scholars have necessitated three basic elements for the all-round development of a region, these are natural resources, institutional social structure and technological development. Natural resources lay the foundation for regional development whereas, the institutional social structure provides a framework of development or backwardness, which is made favourable using the technological development by the people of that region for the region's development. Literacy is one of the main factors that is used for measuring the levels of development on the basis of the above three elements. According to Indian Census definition "Literacy" means "a person who can read and write a simple message in any language with understanding is considered literate" (Census of India, 2011) Literacy rates in India are calculated excluding 0-6 age group of the population.

Review of Literature

Literacy and education are considered as the main driving force of development for a nation. Education and literacy not only control the state of development but also determines it. Education not only develops the personality of a person but it also helps in the development of the region. A number of studies have documented, both theoretically and empirically, the importance of education not only for economic benefits but social too. Krishan (1978) emphasizes a major rise in the female-male ratio in higher education from 14:100 in 1951 to 66:100 in 2001. Women's participation in medical, engineering and technical education has also gone up noticeably in the past few decades. The state-level data reveals that 'the presence of women in higher education finds a stronger correlation with female literacy rate than with the level of urbanization or per capita income. Nath (2001) draws attention to lowest literacy rates in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, which together have about 1/4th of the population of the country. Also, despite having a large number of illiterates, the progress in increasing literacy has been noteworthy, resulting in phenomenal growth of the print media - weekly and daily newspapers, magazines and books, films and television serials, all in regional languages.

Singh (1998) analyzed the emerging trends of female literacy in India and concluded that notwithstanding, enormous social and economic costs of neglect of female education, the study of female literacy in India is that of preponderance illiteracy marked by gender gaps and regional inequalities with the problem compounding over the years. The wide disparity and persistence of acute illiteracy in regions, a matter of both supply-side shortage and demand-side constraints is an issue of serious concern. There seems to be a dialectical relationship between educational progress and social change. Illiterate women are invariably caught in a vicious circle of poverty, repeated childbearing, ill-health, and

powerlessness, lacking the means to break out of their predicament, education. Illiteracy for them becomes a lifelong cul-de-sac contributing to their marginalization within the family, the workplace and public life.

Mehta (1995) focused on patterns and correlates of tribal literacy in India. Physical and economic distance to schools as well as the lack of opportunity for schooling in mother tongue were found to be the main deterrents in the way of tribal literacy in the country. Prior to 1990s also attempts had been made to analyze the trends and regional disparities in literacy. In this context, the works of Gosal (1964), Tirtha (1966), Naik (1971), Krishan and Shyam (1978), Gosal (2001), Sagar (1991), Reddy (1985), Raza and others (1986) and Chandna (1972) may be cited. Panwar and Vyas (1993) worked on planning strategies for removal of disparities in educational development in Rajasthan. These apart, a number of studies on the regional analysis of literacy at Meso/micro scale i.e. state or district or tehsil have also been carried out. The attempts made by Joshi (2000), Mukerji (1968), Sharma (1985), Chitnis (1974), Krishan and Chandna (1974), Banerjee (1975), Siddique (1977), Singh (1979), Schuth (1980), Dutta (1982), and Shastri (1985), fall into the category of regional studies. Yadav, Jetwal and Khan (2018) have studied the spatial patterns of literacy differentials in Hadauti region. Thus, most of the studies, pertaining to literacy, have been confined to

the spatial analysis of this attribute either at national or at the regional level.

Therefore, the educational stage is also a symbol of regional development. The present study is undertaken looking at the dual and important role of education.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to:

1. To determine the state of educational development of Bundi district
2. To study the different dimensions of educational development and its temporal analysis
3. To analyse the data at the tehsil level and find out the regional distribution pattern of educational status

Methodology

The tehsil has been considered the most appropriate unit of study. The study is based primarily on the secondary data obtained from a variety of authentic government sources. The tehsil level data for total, male, female population has been taken from Census of India (2011) General Population Totals, Primary Census Abstract, Rajasthan. Data received from various sources first and then combined it into different groups and tables according to the requirements of the study. For objective fulfilment and factual comparative analysis of data use of maps and various statistical methods have been used in the study.

Study Area

Bundi district is the part of 'Hadoti' region in southeastern Rajasthan and lies between 24°09'11" N to 25°53' 11" N latitudes and 75°30' to 76°21' 30" East longitudes covering an area of 5763 Sq. Km, with a population of 1,113,725 persons as per 2011 census. The district has taken its name from a narrow valley called 'Bundi-ka Nal' where Meena chieftain Jaita erected the Bundi city in the centre of the valley. It is divided into 5 tehsils which are: Bundi, Hindoli, Nainwa, Keshoraipatan and Indragarh. Bundi District is bordered to the north by Tonk District, to the west by Bhilwara District, to the East by Kota District and to the southwest by Chittorgarh District.

Bundi District belongs to Vindhyan and Aravalli formations having three broad groups of soils. The northeastern part is having hard red soils while the southeastern part is covered with black soil formed by weathering of Deccan lavas. The general slope is from northwesterly direction to southeasterly direction. Chambal is the main river of the district. The other rivers are Mej, Mangliand Bajan. The geological formations of the district mainly belong to Vindhyan and Aravallies, the metamorphic series of Archaean rocks consisting gneiss schists, quartzites, limestone, marble, granite and sandstone.

The geographical environment is a basic

determinant of its socio-economic, cultural and political activities. Remarkable features of its surface, physiography and soil compositions make this region a typical physical unit. The region is mainly composed of low hills and discretely distributed plateau area with shallow plains. The area exhibits numerous natural diversities and reflects a queer and confused amalgam of lowland and upland topography.

Spatial Pattern of Literacy

Table 1: Bundi Tehsil wise Literacy Rates since 1971

Tehsil	1971	1981	1991	2001	2011
Hindoli	8.75	11.77	22.16	46.81	53.92
Nainwan	11.90	15.87	26.62	52.47	57.83
Bundi	19.58	22.99	37.01	58.3	63.6
Keshoraipatan	20.29	26.48	38.76	59.42	68.05
Indragarh	61.5	65.54
Bundi District	16.01	20.14	32.75	55.80	62.31

Source: Calculated by authors

The entire district is divided into 3 levels on the basis of 2011 literacy levels.

1. High level (65 percent and more) – On the basis of 2011 literacy data, Keshoraipatan and Indragarh tehsils fall in this category.
2. Medium level (55 percent to 65 percent) – Nainwan and Bundi tehsils come under this category.
3. Low level (55 percent and less) – Only one tehsil Hindoli falls in this category.

During 1971, the reason for the overall low levels of literacy is the lack of peoples' interest in education. Not much effort was undertaken by the government to the aware public for education consciousness. Majority of the population was rural and poor. Children were made to work rather than

providing them with an education. Education, especially female education was not given any importance due to stereosity and backwardness. Girls were confined to domestic help. All these reasons were cumulatively responsible for the low literacy levels in Bundi district. Looking at table 1, we find that in 1971 the literacy of Bundi district was as low as 16.01 percent; whereas it grew at a slower rate and finally reached 62.31 percent in 2011 census. There was a gain of 46.3 percent during the last 40 years. Analysing the male and female literacy levels we see a different picture. In 1981 male literacy levels were below 40 percent. Hindoli which is an undulating terrain had a male literacy of 19.07 percent while Keshoraipatan which was economically advanced had a male literacy of 40.43 percent. Table 2.

Bundi Literacy 1971 – 2011

Literacy Rates (In %)

Table 2: Bundi Tehsil Wise Male Literacy

Tehsils	1981		1991		2001		2011	
	Male Literacy %	Change in Male Literacy	Male Literacy %	Change in Male Literacy	Male Literacy %	Change in Male Literacy	Male Literacy %	Change in Male Literacy
Bundi	33	...	50.64	17.64	72.4	21.76	75.95	3.55
Hindoli	19.07	...	34.77	15.7	64	29.23	68.58	4.58
Indragarh	78.1	...	80.34	2.24
Keshoraipatan	40.43	...	56.54	16.11	75.8	19.26	81.66	5.86
Nainwan	23.52	...	40.93	17.41	71	30.07	73.91	2.91

Source: Calculated by authors

Hindoli and Nainwan tehsils showed a comparative high positive change of 29.23 percent and 30.07 percent respectively in 2011. The results of

literacy programmes and campaigns started yielding results and the male literacy continued to increase in 2011 as well.

Table 3: Bundi Tehsil Wise Female Literacy

Tehsils	1981		1991		2001		2011	
	Female Literacy %	Change In Female Literacy	Female Literacy %	Change In Female Literacy	Female Literacy %	Change In Female Literacy	Female Literacy %	Change In Female Literacy
Bundi	11.57	...	21.43	9.86	42.6	21.17	50.34	7.74
Hindoli	3.55	...	7.86	4.31	27.7	19.84	38.13	10.43
Indragarh	43.3	...	49.57	6.27
Keshoraipatan	10.85	...	18.82	7.97	41.5	22.68	53.5	12
Nainwan	7.39	...	10.38	2.99	32.2	21.82	40.48	8.28

Source: Calculated by authors.

Table 3 shows the data on female literacy in Bundi district from 1981 to 2011. Looking at the above table we find that the percentage of female literacy is very low. In 1981 all the tehsils had the female literacy below 12 percent with Hindoli as low as 3.55 percent and Nainwan tehsil just its double but not touching double digit figure. These tehsils are Gurjar and Mali dominating castes which instead of sending girls to school, indulge them in household work of cattle rearing and vegetable plucking from the farms. In 2001 the data reveals that the female literacy did increase considerably but the fact is still in 2011 their

figures haven't increased much in spite of government policies for the girl child. The tradition of child marriages in the district is also the culprit for low female literary figures.

The map shows that there was some change in female literacy but it was recorded minimum change from 1981 to 2011 in Hindoli while the maximum change that is over 40 percent was seen in Keshoraipatan tehsil of the study area. While the remaining three tehsils recorded a moderate change in female literacy from 1981 to 2011.

Bundi Literacy 1971 – 2011

Educational Facilities

Education is a powerful tool to measure levels of regional development. Education, occupation and income together influence the economic status of society. In the present study development in education is analysed at two levels that is,

1. primary and upper primary schools and
2. secondary and senior secondary schools

The development of college and university level education is negligible compared to the state so its analysis has not been taken for study.

Primary and upper Primary Schools

Education, especially female education was not so popular in Bundi district in 1971. The number of educational institutions in the district was comparatively low. The main reason for this was lack of awareness among the population.

Table 4 Bundi Tehsil wise Change in Number of Educational Institutions

Tehsil	1981		2011	
	Secondary & Sr.Sec Schools (No./1 Lakh Population)	Upper Primary & Primary Schools (No./10 Thousand Population)	Secondary & Sr.Sec Schools (No./1 Lakh Population)	Upper Primary & Primary Schools (No./10 Thousand Population)
Bundi	8.9	9.78	42.28	16.13
Hindoli	7.11	12.38	34.31	17.87
Indragarh	41.1	20.47
Keshoraipatan	8.4	13.21	49.35	18.25
Nainwan	10.8	13.05	41.31	18.51
Bundi District	9.02	11.84	41.36	17.68

Source: Calculated by authors

During 1981 the number of upper primary and primary schools per ten thousand population was 11.84 which increased to 17.68 during 2011. Tehsil wise analysing the data reveals that maximum 20.47

upper primary and primary schools per ten thousand population were recorded in Indragarh tehsil. The figure indicates awareness of the public for education and developed economic status helped achieve this

number. One tehsil Bundi recorded below the district average of 16.13 upper primary and primary schools per ten thousand population.

Secondary and Senior Secondary Schools

During 1971 there were only 17 secondary and senior secondary schools in the entire district which rose to 116 in 2001 and further increased to 458 in 2011. The number of secondary and senior secondary schools per one lakh population was 9.02 in 1981 which increased drastically to 41.36 in 2011. Tehsil wise analysing the data reveals that maximum 49.35 secondary and senior secondary schools per one lakh population were in Keshoraipatan tehsil while three tehsils Hindoli, Indragarh and Nainwan recorded less

than the district average of 41.36. In the socio-economically backward tehsils of the region like Hindoli, girls are made to assist their parents in the collection of farm produce (especially vegetables as this is the major agricultural produce of the area) while in Nainwan girls are given responsibility to graze cattle.

Enrolment in Educational Institutes

During 1971, 49710 students were enrolled in the educational institutes which increased to 95792 during 1981 and to 221402 in 2001 and to 307321 during 2011. During the last 40 years, the enrolment has increased almost six times but the literacy rate does not match this number.

Table 5 Bundi Tehsil Wise Enrolment in Educational Institutes (In Percent)

Tehsil	1971			2011		
	Sec.&Sr.Sec schools	Upper Primary schools	Primary schools	Sec.&Sr.Sec schools	Upper Primary schools	Primary schools
Bundi	45.5	35.45	34.19	38.05	29.27	33.44
Hindoli	7.1	18.05	19.2	18.53	18.06	29.18
Indragarh	11.23	10.79	7.29
Keshoraipatan	29.4	28.91	31.07	14.5	12.46	10.4
Nainwan	18	17.59	15.54	17.69	29.42	19.69
Bundi District	11.76	40.69	47.55	45.36	37.83	16.81

Source: Data taken from DEO Office, Bundi

Conclusions

Literacy has frequently been seen as a must for economic development, social mobility and political stability. Illiteracy, by disparity, has frequently been related to increased poverty, high crime rates, under development, political instability and economic stagnation. Education is very much necessary for the socio-economic development of human beings but education has not received its proper attention, particularly in the case of women. Following steps need to be taken to uplift the district to the national and state level parameters-

1. Establishment of more primary and upper primary schools should be done to increase female enrolment and literacy
2. Secondary schools should be upgraded to senior secondary level so that students drop out rate be minimized
3. The district ranks lowest in terms of higher education as there is no government college in the district other than at the district headquarter so more colleges should come up at tehsil headquarters
4. More educational institutes like Navodaya Vidyalaya should come up in rural places to increase awareness of rural folk for education

All these steps will surely bring a positive change and a literate society will thus help in bringing all round regional development as well as the social development of the district.

References

- Banerjee, M. (1975), "Literacy in Singhbhum, Bihar", *Geographical Review of India*, 37, 2, pp. 151-157.
- Chandna, R.C. (1972): "Scheduled Caste Population in Rural Haryana: A Geographic Analysis", *National Geographical Journal of India*, 18(3&4), pp. 177-186.
- Chitnis, S. (1974), *Literacy and Educational Enrolment among Scheduled Caste of Maharashtra*, Tata Institute of Social Science, Bombay.
- District Statistical Outline, Bundi 1971, 1981, 1991, 2001, 2011
- Dutta, G. (1982), "Analysis of literacy rates in the southern districts of West Bengal", *Geographical Review of India*, Vol. 44, No.32, pp. 19-26.
- Gosal, G.S. (1964): "Literacy in India-An Interpretative Study", *Rural Sociology*, 29(September), pp.261- 77.
- Gosal, R.P.S. (2001), "Sex composition of India's population, 2001: A geographical analysis," *Population Geography*, Vol. 23, No. 1 & 2, pp. 29-40
- Joshi, H. (2000): "Changing Literacy Levels in Rajasthan: A Geographical Analysis", *Geographical Review of India*, 62(2), pp.150-160.
- Krishan, G. and Chandna, R.C. (1974), "Haryana: Working force and its occupational structure," *Manpower Journal*, Vol. 10, pp. 50-72.

- Krishan, G. and Shayam, M. (1978): "Regional Aspects of Urban-Rural Differentials in Literacy in India", *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 13(1), pp.11-22.
- Mehta, S. (1995), "The tribal literacy situation in India," presented at the XVII Annual Congress of the National Association of Geographers, India, held at Jammu, 28-31.
- Mukerji, A.B. (1968), "Spatial Patterns of Literacy in Andhra Pradesh, India", *Selected Papers*, 21 International Geographical Congress, pp. 181-186.
- Naik, J.P. (1971), *Education of the Scheduled Castes (1965-66)*, Occasional Monograph 6, ICSSR, New Delhi.
- Nath, V. (2001), "First results of the decennial census of population: 2001," *Population Geography*, Vol. 23, No. 1 & 2, pp. 41-48.
- Panwar Lalit K. and Vyas S.S. (1993), "Planning Strategies for Removal of Disparities in Educational Development in Rajasthan", in Sheel C. Nuna(ed), *Regional Disparities in Educational Development*, South Asian Publishers Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi.
- Raza, M. and Aggarwal, Y.P. (1986), "Inequalities in the levels of literacy in India: The regional dimensions," in M. Shafi and Mehdi, Raza (eds.), *Spectrum of Modern Geography*, Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, pp. 193-226.
- Reddy, U. B. (1985), "Regional disparities in educational development in India: An inter-state analysis," *Geographical Review of India*, Vol. 47, No. 2, pp. 22-27.
- Sagar, P. (1991), "Regional disparities in literacy of India 1981," *Asian Profile*, Vol. 19, No. 3, pp. 253-66.
- Schuth, K. (1980), "Village literacy and its correlates," in David E. Sopher (ed.), *An Exploration of India: Geographical Perspective on Society and Culture*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York. pp. 130-187.
- Sharma, H.N. (1985), "Sex Disparity in Literacy and Social Topography of Assam", in Mukerji, A.B. and Ahmad, A. (eds.), *India, Inter-India Publication*, New Delhi, pp. 379-401.
- Shastri, P.S. (1985), "Patterns of Tribal Literacy in Vidarbha", *Population Geography*, pp. 40-59.
- Siddique, M. (1977): "The Geography of Literacy in Uttar Pradesh", *Geographical Review of India*, 39(1), pp.374-388.
- Singh, C.P. (1979), "Literacy in a rural population in Meerut District," *Geographical Observer*, Vol. 15, pp. 32-36.
- Singh, Nina (1998), "Female literacy in India: The emerging trends," *Population Geography*, Vol. 20, No. 1&2, pp. 23-36.
- Tirtha, R. (1966), "Areal Patterns of Literacy in India", *Manpower Journal*, 3, pp. 88-118
- Yadav, S., Jetwal, N. and Khan, Z. (2018), "Spatial Patterns of Literacy Differentials in Hadauti Region (2011): A Regional Perspective" *Annals of the Rajasthan Geographical Association*, Vol. XXXV (under print)